

"SOCIAL MEDIA CELEBRITY PAGES AND POLITICAL CHANGE IN ARAB COUNTRIES"

From 2011-2013

Case Study about the role of social media celebrity Face book pages in motivating their audiences

Written by

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ABSTRACT

Social marketing in politics awareness has become common with the increased access and use of social media platforms. Traditionally social media platforms have been used as a channel of marketing for companies and other organizations where they provide details of the products and services they offer and give people an opportunity to provide feedback through comments. Social media platforms come as tools to supporting a political campaigns and political awareness at democracy countries. This research study a famous facebook pages in Arab countries (Tunis and Egypt) throw the spring revolution 2011-2013, to understand if those pages have any effective to motivate their audiences', and rising their political awareness's.

Categories and Subject Descriptors

Social and Behavioral Sciences – Sociology, Psychology

General Terms

Media Management

Keywords

Social marketing; Social media; Media strategy; Marketing strategy; Campaign; Political media awareness.

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1. INTRODUCTION:

Facebook for instance is used by people to post their political opinions and views and this has a major impact on the other users who are likely to get convinced to follow the views of other in making political decisions. Research by Pew Research Centre (2012) for instance shows that 66% of the social media users have at one point used the platforms to post their views and opinions about political issues arising in their nation. A greater number of users have also been involved in commenting on the political posts, following certain candidates, liking and linking to political contents as well as joining groups formed on the social networking sites for politicking. This shows the role that social networking sites are playing in marketing of political views where people get to share their political opinion to others who end up being influenced by this information to make their political decisions (Pew Research Centre , 2012). It is this kind of social marketing of politics that was used as a tool

by activists to gang up citizens against the dictatorial regimes. People formed groups on Facebook that were used to post information criticizing the government and calling for people to rise and fight for their democracy.

Another way in which social networking sites were used in the spring revolution was to organize meetings and demonstrations. The gatherings witnessed in Tahrir Square in Egypt as well as the extensive protests organized in Tunisia are a good example of how Social networking sites were used to bring people from their homes to stage demonstrations. This was mainly the work of bloggers who used the opportunity provided by Facebook and Twitter to organize events and incite people to turn out in large numbers that had never been witnessed in the Arab nations. They were able to voice their support for the turn of events using the media sites where videos of the brutality carried out against the dictators were posted. People continued supporting and encouraging each other on Facebook causing an unrelenting push for their goal and this eventually earned them their long awaited freedom from the hopelessness that they had been living in (Semaan, 2014).

Despite the role played by Facebook and other social media sites in the Arab spring revolution being clear, there are other opinions about who have opposed this fact claiming that the social media does not have any power to topple an authoritarian regime. According to Reuter & Szakonyi, (2013) these scholars have claimed that any authoritarian regime would find ways to overcome the impact of the social media if it was working against them. The authoritarian regimes have been known to control the media such as the television and radio channels where any information that is being relayed to the public has to be approved by the government regulatory bodies. The authoritarian regimes would supposedly use the same strategy to block the social networking sites that were being used to spread propaganda information about the dictators. This is not actually the case as it is not easy for the government to control social media as it does with other media channels. As it was the case with Tunisia, the government was able to block most of the social media sites apart from Facebook which was being used by most of the citizens and it appeared that closing it would cause more problems (Reuter & Szakonyi, 2013).

Many people and political analysts think that social communication across social communication sites in particular (Facebook) is the main cause of the Arab revolutions as well as its support in the Arab world, but no scientific study proves that this theory is valid.

In this research lies in the extent of confirming or refuting this theory, and this is done by

identifying the role of the icons pages of social media in influencing the opinions of their followers, (1) Do the celebrity Facebook pages haven active role in clarifying the political image in the media for the Arab street during the Spring revolutions? (2) Did the celebrity pages participate to raising a political awareness' to educating their followers politically? (3) Do the messages of the social media celebrity pages have an impact on their followers to motivating them to take an action agents the government regime? And how can we utilize such an impact to create political awareness by the media?

Finding the answers to these questions will help in (1) to identify the patterns of human behavior of the celebrities of social media sites, which they use with their recipient audiences. (2) to analyze the political media messages and their impact on the recipient audiences.(3)Provide scientific results to increase awareness of how to plan media messages in social media marketing across social networking sites in the Arab world.

In the following section present some Literature reviews this part deal with previous studies about the impact of social media sites on the receiving public and especially the Facebook. In section 3, describe the methodology we followed in order to collect and distill a political messages awareness in a social media in Celebrities facebook (CFB) pages as a case study in Tunisia and Egypt. In section 4, present all observation and distill the collection information about the pages to understand the environment influencing at the political media messages in the CFB pages. Then in section 5, discuss the findings and answer the three posed research questions. Finally section 6 provides disscasion, conclusion and recommendations.

2. Literature review

This part will deal with previous studies about the impact of social media sites on the receiving public and especially the Facebook and will focus on three main themes:

- The impact of social media sites on individual decisions
- The role of social media sites in impacting collective opinion
- The role of social media sites in the development of political awareness

2.1.The impact of social media sites on individual decisions

If we take into account that social marketing is symmetric to the elements and styles of commercial marketing, then studying how the consumer's individual decisions are taken is an important way to utilize such decisions in the development of future marketing plans.

Therefore, studies show that marketing across social media sites Facebook has a significant influence on the decisions of the individual consumer, and how to evaluate materials and make a purchase.

In the study conducted by **Wei Li, Ayda Darban** about **"The impact of online social networks on consumers' purchasing decision --The study of food retailers"**, it was clear that "Facebook" social networking site helped the consumer to easily identify the products and compare between them. It also contributed to obtaining the views of buyers quickly and thus evaluate the product and make a decision.

Therefore, consumers prefer online social networks because of the special features that distinguish social networking on the Internet. It has provided them with opportunities to share information, experiences and views and compare them with the experiences and views of others.

It also helped the consumer to get recommendations from others about supermarkets and different products before buying. Therefore, the study showed that social media is one of the steps in the purchasing decision of consumers, and that they vary according to varying consumer confidence in the product and in the shops selling food.

On the same level, another study entitled **"The Role of Marketing in Social Media: How Online Consumer Reviews Evolve"** carried out by **Yubo Chen a, Scott Fay b & Qi Wang in 2012**, revealed that consumer behavior and confidence in the brand plays an important role in determining consumer satisfaction and confidence in a purchasing decision. This study revealed that; "the relationships between consumer review posting behavior and marketing variables in social media, and it examines how these relationships evolve as Internet and consumer review websites attract more universal acceptance. Our empirical analysis of automobile data from two years, 2001 and 2008, reveal several important patterns of consumer posting behavior as the Internet has evolved. First, we find that marketing variables affect consumer online posting behavior". The study showed that social media sites play an important role in determining consumer satisfaction about the brand and product through his confidence in the public views and comments on the product and brand. In a similar study, it showed the role of social media sites and the influence of the views of others on the future planning and decision-making.

Pattarawadee Sema conducted a study entitled; **"Does Social Media Affect Consumer Decision-Making?"** to ascertain through a review of selected literature on social media its influence on travelers' decision-making for their future vacations. The study revealed that recommendations by friends or connections on social media also could help consumers

decision-making. Those recommendations could help brand attitudes, purchasing attitudes, and advertising attitudes. The more good responses on the products or services, the more attractive for consumer purchasing. Most of top brands and services notice it and started to focus on social media marketing. The study revealed that approximately 52% of leisure travelers used social media on their trip for the past 12 months to Share their travel experiences. A majority of the social media users (65%) have Used Facebook to both read and post activities. The use of social media in travel planning had a positive influence on increasing actual travel experience sharing behavior and the experience with social media also positively related to actual Travel experience sharing on social media. These result reported that with increased perceived enjoyment, the use of social media increase as a source in travel planning, and level of experience with Social media has a positive influence on sharing travel experiences on social media. This indicates that the consumer trusts the news and social networking sites, which helps him make the decision individually to buy

2.2 The role of social media sites in impacting collective opinion

This theme is focused on highlighting the Arab Studies that show how Arab communities deal with the social media sites, and the extent of benefiting from it.

It reveals the following:

In a study conducted by **Dr. Hatem Saleem Alawneh, on "the role of social media sites in motivating Jordanian citizens to participate in the mass movement"; a field study on trade unionists in Irbid "in November 2012.** Since the beginning of the year (2011), Jordan witnessed, like many Arab countries, a wave of protests and sit-ins and marches demanding reformist changes in the political, economic and social fields. The social media sites allowed the organizers of the activities of this mass movement, to participate and interact with the events at the level of mobilization and motivating public opinion.

This study aimed to identify the role of social media sites in stimulating Jordanian citizens to participate in the activities of the mass movement, using the descriptive and analytical approach of media surveys, both, on a sample of (296) trade unionists in the city of Irbid. The main findings of this study were 50.6 percent of the trade unionists use Facebook, their motivations for using these sites is that they allow them to communicate with friends (28.5%), and offer the opportunity to express their views freely (21.8%) The results showed that (56.6%) of the trade unionists are involved in the mass movement, which calls for conducting reform and change in Jordan, through social media sites. Demanding constitutional reforms topped the list of the mass movement themes, which involved

unionists across social media sites, and got a rate of (14.4%), followed by demanding political, economic and social reforms (14.1%).

The results showed that there was no statistically significant relationship between demographic characteristics of the trade unionists and participation in the mass movement across social media sites.

On the same level, the results of the study by Dr. Saud Saleh Kateb- King Abdul Aziz University, Saudi Arabia 2011, about "New Media and Community Issues" revealed that the Arab world is still conservative about the free expression of its political, social and educational issues, and that social networks have become an outlet for free social networking, which in turn brought significant implications for the rules of freedom of publication and expression of thought and the strengthening of democratic and human rights of young people in the Arab world, and that Arab governments are still conservative about participating in the use of social media sites, especially in the political sphere.

Therefore, the perception of social networks in the Arab region tended either to ignore them or express fear and caution towards them for political or social considerations, or underestimate them as a temporary phenomenon. However, the role played by these networks especially Facebook ,Twitter and YouTube in the political events in the region with the beginning of 2011 made governments and commercial and educational institutions show greater attention to those networks. However, using social media in government, business, educational and social sectors is still weak compared to the latent potential offered by these applications in other developed countries. And despite the considerable potential of those networks, yet their utilization in the Arab world is still weak and did not live up to taking advantage of their available potential and characteristics, whether in the areas of education or by non-profit organizations.

Another study was conducted on "the role of social media sites in affecting change" by Dr. Bushra Jamil Alrawi- Cairo University, 2012. The study aimed to ask the question: Who makes the change? And does the media play a supporting role in social change by strengthening the public domain? The results of the study answered this question as follows , Youth used social media to chat and express emotional issues, and then the youth started to exchange cultural, literary and political views. Social media sites are considered alternative media: It is the "location where criticism is practiced." The social media sites do not represent the key factor for change in society, but it has become an important factor in creating change requirements by creating awareness. The social media sites are open spaces for rebellion and revolution - beginning from overcoming shyness and introversion and ending with revolution on the political systems. The media agenda for social media sites is

shaped through high-profile events that impose themselves. The real political change was not born on the Internet, but it was bred in the street, and new media complemented it. The backwardness and practice of democracy in the Arab world is the result of failure to understand democracy channels and its arguments in thought, and this leads to the rejection of the spread of thought and its prevalence because with regard to power, it is only traded on the level of ideas and perceptions and approaches.

2.3 The role of social media sites in the development of political awareness

A Study entitles "Social Media and Political Engagement" showed that "the use of social media sites has become a tool for political dialogue and interaction in America. And that Some 60% of American adults use either social networking sites like Facebook or Twitter, and a new survey by the Pew Research Center's Internet & American Life Project finds that 66% of those social media users—or 39% of all American adults—have done at least one of eight civic or political activities with social media. " For the researchers: **Lee Rainie** *Director, Pew Internet Project* ,**Aaron Smith** *Research Associate, Pew Internet Project* ,**Kay Lehman Schlozman** *Boston College*,**Henry Brady** *University of California – Berkeley* , and **Sidney Verba** *Harvard University*. The study revealed that 35% of social media users have used the tools to encourage people to vote. Democrats who are social media users are more likely to have used social media to encourage voting, 34% of social media users have used the tools to post their own thoughts or comments on political and social issues. 31% of social media users have used the tools to encourage other people to take action on a political or social issue that is important to them. Some 36% of social-media-using Democrats have done this as have 34% of Republicans. This compares to 29% of independents who are social media users. 21% of those who use belong to a group on a social networking site that is involved in political or social issues, or that is working to advance a cause. There are no major differences by ideology or partisanship when it comes to using social media this way. 20% of social media users have used the tools to follow elected officials and candidates for office.

And a similar study showed that the success of the marketing campaigns for political elections was successful in raising political awareness and ease of choosing the right candidate. **And this is shown by the study "Social Media and Political Campaigns", Kristian Smith, 2012**, The study simply revealed that social media played a great role in the success of President Obama in his first campaign, and that it will continue to support the media communication of political campaigns, as they have a major role in educating the voters. Some findings were Social media has played and will continue to play a significant role in

political campaigns. Social media will play an ever increasing role in campaigns. Through platforms like Facebook, Twitter, and YouTube, political candidates will continue to interact with supporters and receive support in the form of donations and volunteers. There are many opinions from social media experts about the way social media should be used in the future. Some say it should be used to target specific groups for advertising, while others believe it should be used to deeply connect with contributors. No matter how politicians use social media in their campaigns, it will continue to be an important part of the campaign process.

Hypothesis:

Through research and looking at previous studies on this subject, we deduce the following:

- That social media sites do have an impact on individual decisions
- That social media sites do not improve or create a high level of social responsibility for the individual in the Arab world.
- That social media sites do have an effect on increasing political awareness

Literature gap:

However, no studies were conducted on the impact of social media celebrities in the political mobilization or increasing the political awareness among their audiences and followers. This research seeks to clarify the relationship between the proven hypotheses and the researcher's questions in detecting the hypotheses put forward.

So, the study assumes:

- There may be a positive correlation between the effect of increasing political awareness among the recipient audiences and the role of social media celebrities in increasing such awareness.
- There may be a positive correlation between the quality of the messages from social media celebrities and the recipient individuals' decisions.
- There may be a zero relationship between the messages from social media celebrities and social mobilization.

3. Research Methodology

3.1 Case Study:

The research address a sample of the social media celebrities pages at Facebook in the Arab world and in particular in Tunisia and Egypt. Where the page of (We are all Khaled Said) is selected from Egypt, and the page (Revolution's men in Al Karm) is selected from Tunisia.

Chooses two social site celebrity pages at Facebook from different countries were they

were active during Arab Spring Revaluation. The number of followers exceeds fifty thousand persons. Neutral non-governmental page, they represents the voice of the street and the citizens, the pages does not belong to any political party or political organizations that have particular targets and agendas as it written in their profiles, and they apply to these pages media organizations standards by the theories of :Media Richness Theory, Theory participant Democratic, Symbolic Interactions Perspective, and the theory of Public Sphere. From this standpoint Used SWOT analysis and observation to study and distill the environment influencing on the political media messages in CFB pages . Also, to explore a social media marketing strategy they used to high rising of political awareness for their followers, and measure the values and standards of their media messages.

3.2 content analyses:

Methods of collect and Data Analysis, during the period between 2011 and 2013, the first step was collect the most higher social interactive in the pages, from different political awareness messages in the pages (video ,image, slogan, comic ,quote) comparing between number of followers and the numbers of interactive in different post.

The second step was to observe and distill the political media messages the pages used patterns for each social media type based on the criteria shown in Table 1.

Social Media Type	Criteria
Video	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of views • Number of likes • Number of Shears • Number of comments • Type of videos • What are user comments?
Image	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of likes • Number of Shears • Number of comments • What are user comments? • Type of usage (e.g. news, announcements, answers, etc.)
Slogan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of likes • Number of Shears

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of comments • What are user comments? • What is the political message in this slogan?
Comic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of likes • Number of Shears • Number of comments • What are user comments? • why they use a comic? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is the political message in this comic?
Quote	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of likes • Number of Shears • Number of comments • What are user comments? • why they use a quote? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is the political message in this quote?

Table 1. Criteria used for exploring the media message in usage patterns for CFB Pages
4. Case Study

4.1 The story behind the pages:

4.1.1 Revolution in Tunisia:

Tarek Tayeb Mohamed Bouazizi, a Tunisian young man, who on Friday December 17th, 2010, set fire to himself in front of the headquarters of Sidi Bouzid governorate in protest against the Sidi Bouzid municipal authorities' confiscation of the carriage he was using to sell fruits and vegetables to earn a living, and to condemn the governorate authorities' refusal to accept a complaint he wanted to submit against the policewoman Fadia Hamdi, who slapped him in public and said to him in French: *Dégage* or Get out). This word became the slogan of the revolution to overthrow the President, as well as the logo for successive Arab revolutions (Al Hiwar, 2010). Bouazizi tried to meet with one of the officials, but to no avail. He then returned to the market and told his vendor colleagues that will set himself on fire, but they did not take his words seriously. Bouazizi stood in front of the municipal building and poured paint thinner on himself and set himself on fire. This led to a popular uprising

and a revolution that lasted nearly a month and toppled President Zine El Abidine Ben Ali. As for Mohammed Bouazizi, he died 18 days after setting fire to himself. No one expected that such an incident can develop, but it did develop into a protest movement, which benefited from the tribal cohesion in the region, the Bouzidi area, where tribal affiliation still has value, and the cultured and educated revolutionary youth use modern tools of social media for communication and publicity of this incident, its events and developments, as well as conducting discussions around it (Shorooq newspaper, 2014). The Mohamed Bouazizi's incident led to protests by the people of Sidi Bouzid in the next day, Saturday 18 December 2010, where confrontations of solidarity with Bouazizi took place between hundreds of young people in Sidi Bouzid region and the security forces. The demonstration was to protest against the high rate of unemployment, marginalization and exclusion in the Sidi Bouzid region. Events quickly evolved into violent clashes and a popular uprising, which included most regions of Tunisia, where people came out in big rallies to demand work and the rights of citizenship and equality of opportunity and development. (BBC, 2011). This uprising forced President Zine El Abidine Ben Ali, who had ruled the country with an iron fist for 23 years- to step down from power and flee the country surreptitiously to Saudi Arabia on January 14, 2011. And the Page (Thawrat Rigal Al Karm) is the most famous revolutionary page that appeared to coincide with the Tunisian revolution, supporting the Tunisian revolution and supporting the Tunisian cause.

4.1.2 Revolution in Egypt:

(KolenaKhaledSaeid which means in English "We are all Khaled Said") is a page on the social networking site "Facebook". It was established in 2010 by the activist Wael Ghonim after the incident of the young Egyptian Khaled Said, who died as a result of torture by police informers during the application of emergency law for 30 years.

Mohammad Saeed Sobhi Qasim is young Egyptian from the city of Alexandria. He was twenty eight years old when he was killed by Egyptian police informers. It seems that the policemen - who wore civilian clothes at the time of the crime - wanted to search Khalid as they thought is authorized to them under the emergency law. So, when Khaled entered an Internet cafe near his home, he was attacked by two people who beat him to death in front of many witnesses in Sidi Gaber area, Alexandria. (BBC, 2010.). The killing of Khaled Said brought a wave of popular anger in Egypt and reactions from international human rights organizations, followed by a series of peaceful protests in Alexandria and Cairo, organized by human rights activists who accused the Egyptian police of constantly practicing torture under the state of emergency. The death of Khaled Said came as part of a series of human

rights violations by the police in Egypt, and the Egyptian and international human rights organizations documented this escalating pace of violations in the years prior to this incident as a reaction of the security state to increasing public concern and the growing popular protests on the living and political conditions, and the growing involvement of large segments of young people in politics, social activism and citizen journalism, which monitor the failures of officials and government corruption and the growing demands movements and human rights violations (Ilaaf newspaper,2011).

Despite that physical abuse and premeditated murder by the police was a permanent phenomenon attendance in the Egyptian society, and become rampant in the last years of Mubarak's rule, but analysts saw that Khaled Said being from the middle class-which traditionally didn't suffer much from such violations unlike the lower and impoverished classes- led to sympathy from wide segments of the public sector, who saw Khaled as an example of what their children can suffer, which contributed lobbying against what happened (AlShrooq AlGadeed, 2011).

The web Page (Kolena Khaled Saeid which means in English "We are all Khaled Said") was established on Facebook to show solidarity with him and it gained more than 4,000 thousand members in less than one hour, and 184000 members within 10 days of publication of the news (Akhir Al Kalam, 2011). This was proof of the state of popular anger that had escalated across Facebook in protest against the killing of Khaled Mohammed Said, who died after being dragged by two informants from Sidi Gaber police station. Members' comments reflected severe anger and objections, and activists considered the killing of Khaled as a new condemnation against the extension of the emergency law that allowed the informants to practice such inhuman treatment with Khaled. The fan's of this Facebook page currently exceed two million people.

The human rights protesting movement, spurred by the death of Khaled Said, is considered one of the harbingers of the January 25 revolution. At the forefront of rioters on January 25, 2011, were many of the activists who were touched by that crime and built their networks around the Khaled Said Facebook page, and other communication tools in cyberspace and on the ground around human rights organizations working in various fields of human rights.

The revolutions in Arab countries such as Tunisia and Egypt have been heavily linked with the social media. Activists are reported to have greatly relies on the social sites such as Facebook to influence people to turn against their leaders.

In his article Beaumont (2011) outlines details of how the social media contributed to the spring revolution with citizens and young people turning to their phones to demonstrate as

opposed to the common use of barricades.

Eventually these pictures and videos find their way to the social media platforms for the whole world to see and this is described as the main reason for the uprising witnessed in the Arab nations. Beaumont (2011) goes on to point out how people shared details of their participation in the demonstrations and their disapproval of the Arab leaders openly. This kind of increased access to details on Facebook was critical for the activists in getting people to turn out for demonstrations against the dictatorial regimes and keep on fighting despite the force used by the governments against them. (Beaumont, 2011)

4.2 Media in Arab world before and after revolution:

4.2.1 Media in Tunisia:

Before the Tunisian revolution, the Tunisian media was monopolized by the state through the official public institutions. There were nine radio stations and two TV channels whose role was to support the official political opinion throughout twenty-three years. And even the private TV channels before the revolution, which were given licenses according to strict pre-conditions that prevent them from deviating from the government line. As for the private radio stations, they were monopolized by the ruling family of former President Zine El Abidine Ben Ali.

The written press cannot be excluded from political control, as the newspapers were dominated by the state, through the external communication agency which controls (ads), and therefore penalizes anyone who deviates from the ruling system. And even the two opposition newspapers "Al Mawqif" and "Moatinoon" have been closely monitored and their distribution stopped because of their belief in professional media and freedom of expression in the media.

The few electronic websites, most of which had economic orientation, avoid talking politics. The most famous sites were; "Business News" and "African Manager" and "WabManager Center" (Al-Araby Al-Jadeed is a London-based pan-Arab news).

But after the revolution, voices and pens were liberated and Tunisia witnessed an unprecedented media explosion. The number of radio stations has reached more than fifty radios and TV reached more than 15 TV channels. The number of paper-based newspapers and magazines reached 200, between daily, weekly and periodical. As for web sites, which are only interested in political affairs, it reached hundreds. Tunisia is known today as " a real televised explosion " making the number of new channels these days 39 , ranging from experimental broadcasting to broadcasting on the Internet in the first stage and

preparations to start broadcasting on satellite (Arab Broadcasting Union - Arab league).

This numerical approach reflects the quality of the media speech, which is marketed by these media channels. It is a liberal speech free of all restrictions, which in some cases becomes chaos. The laws and structures tried to reduce such chaos through laws that take into account the Tunisian media gains (Noureddine AlHad Mahmoud, Arabi Algadeed, 2015), where this phenomena, which hit the Tunisian media was considered mere improvisation due to the "knowledge poverty" among workers in this sector, pointing out that the media in Tunisia had been subject to a purely technical perspective that is not related to humanities and social sciences that reflect the pulse of the street. (Al Jazeera Centre for Studies, report on the reality of the Tunisian media, 2014)

So the legal framework governing the media work in Tunisia came with the issuance of Decrees 115 and 116 in November 2012. Those two decrees organized the media sector in Tunisia through the confirmation of the freedom of expression and the rejection of all corporal punishment that journalists might be exposed to as a result of expressing their views and positions.

Also in the context of regulating the sector, the Ministry of Information was abolished and other revisionist structures were created to oversee the sector, including the "Independent Commission for Audiovisual Communication", which was established on May 3, 2013 on the occasion of World Press Freedom Day, which is a constitutional revisionist entity that ensures media freedoms without touching the laws regulating the media industry.

These liberal laws have been confirmed in the Tunisian Constitution, which was declared on January 27, 2014, and which came to enshrine the principle of freedom of opinion and expression and freedom of press, and is a further guarantee for Tunisian journalists after the revolution, ensuring that freedom of the media is one of the biggest gains (Al-Jazeera Center for Studies, 2014).

After the Tunisian revolution, the violations against media freedoms continued to be documented, according to the Tunisian Journalists union, even though the tools and those who committed the crimes were different from before, making the media scene locked into all these interactions. But there is a significant change to the reality of media freedoms in Tunisia after the revolution, and it seems clear, as the media freedom in Tunisia advanced by 3% compared with other countries that have seen different revolutions. Tunisia came a long way on the road to freedom of opinion and expression, through the enactment of laws guaranteeing freedom of journalistic work (Kamal al-Obeidi, on the sidelines of the International Day for the freedom of the press held between 3-7 May)

The abolition of censorship and restrictions that were imposed on the freedom of journalistic work, and adoption of free access to information law, in addition to the establishment of a revisionist media body and its rules, refers to the transmission of media from the ruling authoritarian regime to granting journalists the right to perform their duties freely. We must also talk about the restrictions that were imposed on the granting of licenses for media organizations, compared to the current period where 12 licenses were granted to private radio stations and 5 TV stations. This was as part of a clear license terms, which focused on professional media work, its independence, and the separation between the ruling regime and the work of journalists. (Najwa Hammami. Wwww.madacenter.org 46 magazine published by the Palestinian Center for Development and Media Freedoms "Mada" number VII / July 2012)

4.2.2 Media in Egypt:

The Egyptian media, both the written and the visual media, played an undeniable role in the case of the political movement that preceded the 25th January 2011 revolution. This was due to three factors: First, the relative margin of freedom enjoyed by the media, and secondly: the reasonable degree of professionalism that characterized workers this sector, and thirdly: the political vacuum and the weakness of state institutions at the end of the Mubarak era, whether the parliament or parties (Al Jazeera- Center for Media Studies). Where the global media sought to fill this vacuum and some TV programs on private satellite channels became arenas for discussion and political debate that was supposed to be under the umbrella of the parliament or within the corridors of political parties. But this role was ruled by undeclared understandings between the ruling regime and the owners of these channels and newspapers regarding a number of red lines that cannot be crossed without being penalized by the state. Especially that most of the owners of these channels are businessmen, and their interests were directly linked to the ruling regime, (Al Jazeera- Center for Media Studies). So, the freedom given to the media was limited to the criticism of some of negativities and corruption in the society and state institutions. It was a freedom with specific and conditional limit, which didn't allow it to engage in specific issues, such as hereditary rule or criticize the president, his family and inner circle. Perhaps this explains the confusion, loss of balance when the media found itself able to communicate with the public in the first days of the revolution until the departure of Mubarak. The moment of Mubarak's departure was a milestone in the march of the Egyptian media, which suddenly found itself

free of all security and administrative restrictions that it was subjected to for decades. The existence of massive media freedom, and the fall of the restrictions led to "information chaos", and was associated with the emergence of dozens of private satellite channels and newspapers. This added to the media chaos functioned without controls or rules governing media performance, as the transitional authority of the military junta which took power did not take any steps to reorganize the Egyptian media legislatively or structurally in line with the new reality. With the beginning of the state of division between the political forces that participated in the revolution, which emerged with the new referendum on constitutional amendments in March 1, 2011, the Egyptian media found itself part of this debate through the great emphasis on the conflict between Islamists on the one hand, and secularists and liberals on the other hand (Mohammed Shoman, 2014). The parties' newspapers conducted information campaigns to promote their ideas against the other, without taking into account the benefit of the nation, which needed stability and everyone's support for reconstruction ". (sawasyah Center for Human Rights, 2011). And with the deepening of the political division the media, both government and private became a tool of political and social conflict. This was obvious in all movements and political trends in Egypt since March 2011 referendum until now.

And the Egyptian media witnessed a new very serious phase after June 30th 2013 and the subsequent removal of former President Mohamed Mursi and the start of a campaign against all supporters of the Muslim Brotherhood. Since that date, the media clearly turned into an explicit tool in the political conflict between the new transitional authority and the Muslim Brotherhood and their supporters. Some media in Egypt became a tool aimed at a particular group, which the Muslim Brotherhood and their supporters. (Mohammad Shoman 0.2013).

In light of the current reality experienced by the Egyptian media now, many people believe that the biggest victims of this reality are mainly: professionalism and Freedom (Byan, of the Arabic Network for Human Rights, 2013). Some media reports of some of the organizations that are concerned with freedoms, reported what is happening in Egypt, where they see that Egypt's image and the freedom of the press have declined from what it was even before the January 25 revolution. This was a result of the harassment and prosecution campaigns, which foreign and Egyptians alike reporters were subject to, as well as arresting dozens of them either during their coverage of the demonstrations of the Muslim Brotherhood or even other demonstrations, such as the demonstrations regarding the third anniversary of the January 25 revolution. (Byan, 2013).

The reports and statements from human rights organizations that are concerned with press

freedom draw a grim picture of the reality of press and media freedom, which are now subject to unprecedented restrictions since July 2013. The Arabic Network for Human Rights violations reported that in the period between June 6 and until August 6 it found 1000 cases against press freedoms by the Egyptian security services (Byan, 2013). As for the Organization (reporters without borders, 2013), it issued a statement condemning what it described as heavy press violations following two months after the military seized power. The Organization said in a statement issued in September 2013 that "after two months, we found out that the outcome of grave violations against journalists and media persons was really serious, as 82 journalists were arbitrarily arrested and 7 of them are still in detention, while 22 media persons were assaulted either by police or demonstrators (reporters without borders, 2013).

The US New Yorker newspaper published a report in May 2014 entitled "in Egypt, journalism is a crime"; where the newspaper talked in its report about the comparison between the situation during and after the revolution of January 25, 2011 and the situation now. The paper reviewed the harassment and threats against journalists currently enforced by the Egyptian authorities. It pointed to the decision of the judicial authorities to arrest twenty workers in Al Jazeera network, including four foreign journalists. Rather, the restrictions on foreign journalists is no longer limited to the authorities, according to the newspaper, but it spread amongst ordinary citizens who support the current regime (THE NEW YORKER-Journalism 2014).

The increased use of social media in the society has resulted in people using it as a stage for reporting and disseminating political news and views to other members of the society. People are becoming more vocal about their political views on the social media which was not the case in the past where people relied on the media channels and newspaper to get political news and there was no opportunity to share their views. The increased use of the social media platforms by citizens to air their political views has also come due to the fact that there is minimal control of the platform by the government as compared to other channels such as television, radio and newspapers. Most of the governments especially in the dictatorial regimes control the media channels by regulating what is reported if it is likely to incite the citizens against the government (Wang & Mark, 2013).

4.3 The CFB pages as media industry

The governments in the Arab countries failed to use social media as a channel to communicate to the citizens opting to rely on the television and media stations which were heavily controlled. This meant that the governments lost touch with most of the youths who spend most of their time on the social networks. The fact that the television and radio

channels as well as other common media in these countries were heavily controlled by the government resulted to the citizens relying on the information that they got from the social media which exposed the government dealings without any form of control. As expected most of the information on the social media was against the government with the activists using the opportunity to reveal how the governments had rendered the people hopeless. There was no participation of the government in these conversations to counter the criticisms made against it and the people increasingly developed a negative attitude towards their leaders before they finally resolved to oust them out of the office. This was a major failure by the governments to keep off the social networking sites where it would have also carried campaigns to show the public that the criticism raised by the activists was actually not true. Governments in most of the countries today use social media as a channel where they post information about their development strategies and what they have been able to do. This in some way helps to win the trust of majority of the citizens who doubt the criticism of the activists and bloggers and opt to support the government. This did not happen with the Arab governments which opted to ignore social media in the period before the spring revolution (Effing, Hillegersberg, & Huibers, 2013).

If it the Facebook pages on social media are deemed as a media organization and measured accordingly, including its elements that confirms its role and its societal acceptance. According to media theories such as: the media Media Richness Theory, and the theory of democratic participation, and the Symbolic Interactions Perspective, the theory of Public Sphere, we can measure its values and standards and its media messages from this standpoint.

We will use SWOT to measuring the strength and weaknesses facing these Facebook pages as media organizations and what are the opportunities and challenges they may face.

Table 2- SWOT Analysis for (We are all Khaled Said) & (Revolution's men in Al Karm):

Strength	Weakness
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • without limitations • mutual exchange • freedom of expression • humanitarian sympathy with the issue 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • collision with the dominance of traditional media • doubting the credibility of the events and news superficial media discourse and ideological generalizations
Opportunities	Threats

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planning for emergence • Public safety and media crises 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enact protection and censorship laws on websites • Might be a platform for threats to internal security • impact on the social, moral and cultural values of the society
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4.3.1 Strengths of social networks from a communication/media

perspective 4.3.1.1 Without limitations:

The internet is characterized by several features that make it an effective means, including: interactive nature, and the difficulty of controlling and monitoring the Web sites, and the widening social base of users, and not being constrained by geographical and political boundaries. Also the recipient audience changed from a mere user and consumer anonymous to the media message to an active participant in the formation of that message. It also encourages achieving greater democracy in the society, and it led to the integration of various media, and made media freedom an inescapable fact, as well as being based on a multi-media modal, which easily spreads and has universal access. It segments its audience, and is untimely and facilitates communication regardless of the specifications and standards of the originator of the content. It also contributes to cultural convergence with other societies in the world, and shortening the distance of communication with various parts of the world as well as contributes to the globalization of public opinion.

The revolution in Tunisia and the spread of its events across social media has contributed significantly to impacting the case in Egypt and other Arab countries. And the views and supporting statements were delivered by all nationals inside and outside their countries.

4.3.1.2 Mutual exchange:

Among the basic features of social networks, is that it enables individuals to practically discover their interests, and search for solutions to their problems with other people, similar to them, or had similar experiences. So, they offer their expertise and experiences, for these people, (Lusk, 2010), and the ability to send e-mails across social networks, and provide full and immediate information on the issue of interest to the social network, and to facilitate follow-up of what is published or broadcast in the media or on the Web sites regarding the issue. Also, providing information to the media persons about many of the issues raised, and help those in charge of command of these networks to recruit volunteers to participate in political issues and events they are interested in, as well as fundraising and obtaining

financial support and in-kind assistance from citizens. Also, the possibility of meeting persons who can provide assistance in public life, and meet new and diverse acquaintances. It can also be considered as a platform for new form of self-expression, which increases the individual's confidence in himself.

4.3.1.3 Freedom of expression:

Social networking websites contributed to a massive balance of freedom of expression without fear of any prosecution. It also helps individuals adapt to their community and communicate with each other, as well as serve to improve the level of discourse and dialogue between members of the society and express opinions without fear or hesitation. It is also useful in knowing how the others think and their opinions about various issues, and can be useful in supporting the decisions leading to success or opposition.

The Facebook Page (KolenaKhaledSaeid which means in English "We are all Khaled Said") became an icon of the Egyptian revolution, and played an important role in the field of political and national awareness. The Page has many political positions and activities at all levels. It also played a role during the Egyptian presidential election in 2012 when it proposed the Vermont document (AlShorooq, 2012) on the presidential candidate Mohamed Mursi, within the presence of many political figures, which contributed to the national powers support to Mursi against his candidate Ahmed Shafiq.

The Page also made a lot of criticism on the negative aspects of the government in the reign of President Mohamed Mursi, where some facts were published such as: the use of policy in the exam papers and other.

4.3.1.4. Sympathy with the humanitarian issue:

The humanitarian sympathy with the most famous Facebook pages contributed to the high number of supporters and followers of the pages. The emotional media messages had a significant impact on mobilizing large numbers in the march of solidarity against Khaled Said's incident during the police day. And the Facebook Page played an important role in calling for the big demonstrations on January 25, which was the beginning of the Egyptian revolution. The page called for organizing an event on the police Day on 25th January along the lines of what was done by some pro-democracy political movements in Egypt, such as the April 6th Movement in 2009. But after the flight of Tunisian President Zine El Abidine Ben Ali, Wael was influenced by the views of the members of the page and changed the event to what he called: "revolt against torture, unemployment, corruption and injustice" and that on the fourteenth of January 2011. This was the first call to the January 25 Revolution (Movement Began with Outrage and a Facebook Page that gave it an outlet - NY Times)

4.3.2 Weakness in CFB pages:

4.3.2.1 The dominance of traditional media

Within the dominance of traditional media, there is a tendency for the Arab citizen to resist the mainstream media through exposure to sources of information that are consistent with his values and attitudes and trends, and getting away from the media, which collide with those values, attitudes and trends. Activists in alternative media provide the information needed for social and political movement such as meetings and sit-ins, demonstrations and addresses of the target figures and targeted entities with protest, forming the solidarity networks between those interested in public issues. Thus, the alternative media goes beyond the mere provision of information that aim to mobilize crowds.

In Tunisia for instance the government under the leadership of Ben Ali was successful in blocking most of the social media sites except for Facebook. By the time the government realized the impact that the social media was having in the uprising, there was already a large number of people in Tunisia using Facebook and this meant that blocking the site would bring about more problems. Facebook eventually became the main platform on which the Ben Ali regime was toppled by the citizens of the nation. Other governments also attempted to control the use of the internet to stop the revolution but this was not successful (Reuter & Szakonyi, 2013)

4.3.2.2 Doubting the credibility of the news and events:

The "alternative media" is a warning bell to the traditional media of newspapers and magazines and radio and TV channels that people feel frustrated towards and doubt its credibility and feel bad about the difficulty to access or influence it, and the inability to participate in the formulation of its media messages. This must push the different alternative media (such as social media) to get rid of negativities that the traditional media practiced over the decades. Alternative media needs to be honest and pay tremendous efforts to correct the mistakes of the traditional media and increase their credibility and their association with the layman and open their doors to other views. They need to confirm their messages through documented media images and live broadcast of events. In Egypt, it played a role in the completion of the goals of the revolution and denouncing the killings and beatings in: balloon - Maspero - Mohamed Mahmoud - the events of the Council of Ministers - Port Said Massacre (Ashrooq, 2012)

4.3.2.3 The superficial media discourse and ideological generalization:

The "alternative media" is suffering from being superficial and using generalizations when asking for opinions, and these problems may make it more of a threat to the cultural system

of the Arab nation, where the Arab street is suffering from serious thinking problems that make its views superficial and using generalizations and linked more to rumors and ideologies and slogans that meet its desires, even if its illogical or not supported by history and science (Emad Bakkar,2007).

4.3.3 Threats on social networks

4.3.3.1 The enactment of protection and government censorship of websites laws: The announcement by the Egyptian Interior Ministry of the implementation of a project for the control of social networks has caused a lot of controversy about the extent of its legitimacy and its impact on civil liberties, and the extent of its relationship with the protection of the individual and the security of the society. This comes in light of a number of variables, which are; the increasing number of Internet users and the escalation of the size of the risks associated with networks Social, which have emerged as a new threat to national security, whether by international intelligence agencies or terrorist groups, or by using it in piracy and cybercrimes. This coincided with its transformation into an important platform for opinion and expression, and within the process of transformation in the nature of rights and freedoms

4.3.3.2 Threatening the internal security of the state:

Despite the positive role of social networks in the process of change and reform during the transitional period, and during the waves of change on January 25 and June 30, it revealed a negative role, which is now increasingly with the weakness of confrontation and lack of awareness. It is now affecting the nature of the relationship between state and society through the deployment of lack of confidence trends that have a negative impact on the structure of society. The open electronic environment, which crosses all borders, gave the opportunity for third parties to intervene in internal affairs. It may be considered as a platform to launch media campaigns against the internal security of the state:

The Egyptian reality shows that social networks are used for extortion, identity theft and defamation and libel crimes, not to mention publishing immoral and destructive ideas within the society.

4.3.3.3 The impact on ethical, social and cultural controls in the society: The Egyptian reality shows that social networks are used for extortion, identity theft and defamation and libel crimes, not to mention publishing immoral and destructive ideas within the society. There is another impact regarding wasting time and manpower by millions of Egyptian youth and its

impact on work and production values, and family and social relations. These new challenges impose the need for a balance between the right to use social media and preventing its use without posing a threat to the security of society. This calls for the need for having controls on the use process, that is to deal with those risks according to their outstanding features, which requires a comprehensive strategy that does not only focus on the security solution but takes into account all the other social, economic and cultural dimensions. The Egyptian Constitution in Article "57" article 2 stipulated that: e mail and phone confidentiality should be protected. This was confirmed by the article "99", which considered the attack on the rights and freedoms a crime of no statute of limitations. In addition, there is the modernization of the legal framework that preserves the privacy and security of individuals through the adoption of the fight against cyber crime and the protection of Personal Information Act. It is also important to safeguard the role of the individual in bearing his own responsibility and developing his knowledge regarding the safe use, and strengthening the role of civil society and the media in raising awareness, and the judicial and parliamentary oversight on the performance of the security services, and the dissemination of information security culture. This calls for investing in the development of the technology industry and the culture of creativity and innovation among young people instead of investing in the field of control and spyware programs (Adel Abdel Sadek, social networking between control and freedom, (Al-Ahram, June 7, 2014). The Egyptian Dar al Fatwa issued a statement, which revealed a set of ethical, social and cultural controls, which must be observed by users of social networking sites while browsing, most notably ensuring truth and reliability when requesting data, information and during circulation, and the emphasis on the protection of intellectual property rights and the laws of cyberspace. It was also pointed out the need to preserve the Islamic and cultural identity of the nation, and not being misled by the dangers of uncontrolled openness, as well as the commitment to the Islamic cultural values , characterized by integrity, respect, dialogue and transparency.

4.3.4 Future opportunities of social media:

4.3.4.1 Contingency planning

The use of social media on a large scale can serve a variety of purposes. Social media played an increasing role in emergencies and disasters over the years, and Facebook became the media center for emergencies as it supported many relevant organizations in emergency situations, including information systems for crises management, humanity and freedom. And humanitarian disasters and community outreach. Due to the ease of communication with a large segment of users due to the availability of social media icons in various means of

communication, social media can be used as a tool for emergency management. It can include regular use for issuing warnings. And social media can be used to receive the victim's requests for assistance and for the dissemination of cultural, social, and political awareness and to assess damages.

4.3.3.2 Public safety and media crises:

Social media have been used for the deployment of a wide range of public safety information before, during and after the occurrence of various incidents. Before the incident (or in the absence of the accident), social media offers the chance for many organizations to manage emergency preparedness by providing information to the citizens. Socialmedia is also used for the purposes of community outreach and customer service by soliciting feedback on the issues related to public safety and national and community security.

4.4 The general view of the pages:

4.4.1 AlKarm Men of the revolution Page:

The media political messages on “the Men of the revolution AlKarm Page” are characterized by sarcasm and religious orientation that are meant to ignite a revolution and gain the support of followers.

From the comprehensive observation of “the Men of the revolution AlKarm Page”, we can see that the page is like an unstructured archive file, which carries a lot of the political media messages that don't include political awareness, a lot of political messages were published without justification or clarifying what is beyond the political media message. The Page left it up to the reader to understand what the media message means if he follows events and declared political news in other media. This random style in posting political media messages does not intend at all to spread political awareness among its followers, according to the media social marketing strategy, which aims to define the message and make its goals clear to the receiving public. Media messages on “the Men of the revolution AlKarm Page” included pictures and sayings and graphics and logos that carry a lot of sarcastic style and revolutionary phrases that suggest threats. Its mission is not to create political awareness of the receiving public (A.S,1).

The political analysis of the events and political decisions doesn't bear the necessary media expertise that carries political awareness that facilitates exploring the political future of the revolution. The political media messages in the Page are vague and unclear and directed to the clear revolutionary mindset, and it lacked the intellectual and political maturity.

Most of the media messages on the Page included many terrorist sentences, and images and logos associated with the religious orientation and not political awareness and

understanding. Most of the media messages were associated with Quranic verses urging revolution and the defense of religions a general orientation of the page (A.S,2).

The sarcastic style mocked political change or political symbols as a kind of rejection of the political decision without mentioning logical reasons to explain the reasons for the rejection of the political decision (A.S ,3).

4.4.2 We are all Khaled Said Page

We are all Khaled Said Page is characterized by being objective in its media offerings and inclusiveness in posting and analysis of the news.

It is noticeable that We are all Khaled Said Page is considered an informative reference for many of the events of the revolution in Egypt. It includes classified pages for each demonstration, event and incident that happened within the history of the January 25 revolution. The Page helped in analyzing the reality of the Egyptian street and knowing the views and political and public orientation during the Revolution of 2011- 2013. The Page wasn't limited to being the carrier and analyst of the news received from the government media, but it also contributed to the identification of the followers' trends and opinions through conducting simple questionnaires about any incident or demonstration or political position.

The general orientation of the page is to confirm the national unity and move away from religious discrimination (A.S 4a,4b)

The Page was not limited only to creating political media awareness, but it also archived economic and social events, and contributed to illustrating hope and stress political change through posting motivating media messages such as pictures, news, sports achievements, motivational sayings and historical political achievements of Egypt. It used media marketing strategies in all their forms, whether through calling for events, organizing marches and rallies, the publication of posters and videos images, and conducting political awareness seminars. The photo media messages swept through the bulk of the media messages published in the page, and the pictures of martyrs had the largest share of the published images. At the social marketing they don't focus on institutions' names, they are focusing more on the themes and images. Too much emphasis upon the visual recognition of brand: colours, design, print .Image play an important role in those campaigns, Images and themes are a reflection of the self images and culture. Identity becomes clearer once they express the means of expression. Brand Identity sends out a clear single message amongst a plethora of actions and slogans. We are all Khaled Said Page kept reminding its followers and celebrated the anniversary of his death over the past three years from the date of the

Egyptian revolution. This Social marketing advertisement contributed to stimulating and confirming its followers' sympathy with the objectives of the Page and its political orientation. The Logo (Revolution healthy) was adopted as the slogan for this promotional campaign in memory of the revolution martyr in 2013. The media analysis of news and political events was characterized by objectivity and conscious media dialogues, and although most of the visual media messages were not labeled, but the repetition of similar images or events sends a clear media message about the idea adopted by Page and about its intellectual orientation.

5. Findings:

5.1 Political Media Messages in the CFB pages:

To address the first research question "What kind of social media messages in the celebrity face book pages used to clarifying the political image in the media for the Arab street during the Spring revolutions ?" Figure 1 shows the kinds of political media messages at the (Thawrat Rigal Al Karm) and measured the followers social interactive.

8,000

7,000

6,000

5,000

4,000

3,000

2,000

1,000

0

video image slogan Comic Qoute over all

view

like

shear

comment

Figure 1. Percentage of Political Media Messages at (Thawrat Rigal Al Karm)

And through comparison between the number of followers on the Page and the number of the followers' social interaction on the page's official website, we note that there is a regressive relationship between the number of followers of the Page and among the proportion of the most interactive media messages.

Where the number of followers of the page reached 51.798, and the fans of the page reached 4,447, according to the page chart for during the week in which the current research was conducted; December 9, 2015. As the number of followers exceeds the proportion of social interaction with media messages on the page. Views of the video *(A.S.No,5) reached 7553, which is the biggest percentage in the social interaction of followers, while the proportion of the comments amounted to less than the proportion of

*Appendices' Sample Number

social interaction with the media message. The number of likes of statements and comic(A.S.No,8) and the video were close, and the visual media message got the highest percentage of likes; 1076. Comments are the lowest ratio in all the most interactive media messages by followers, where the highest rate on the visual message was 34 while the caricature got 2 comments. And with reference to the type of comments that received the highest proportion, we find that it is the sarcastic image(A.S.No,6) of the badly dressed military leader, as most of the comments were jokes and comments about the length of the trousers.

The rate of participation for each of the video media message and the picture (A.S.No,6) media message was close. Also the rate of participation in the media message of the quote(A.S.No,9) and the slogan(A.S.No,7) was close. The caricature got the least share between the followers.

Therefore, we note that the direct message and picture messages are more pronounced in the transfer of information and delivery of media message, and written messages come in the second degree in the social interaction of followers.

Given the followers' total social interactions about media messages, we find that there is a very big difference between the number of views and the other types of social interaction. And this confirms the individual's freedom of choice and social interaction with the published media messages.

And with reference to the theories of the study find that it was not proved right regarding the individual decision and the sent media messages. There is an inverse relationship between the number of views and number of followers and between the individual decisions

to participate in the social interaction of media messages.

Figure .2 shows the kinds of political media messages at the (We are all Khaled Said) and measured the followers social interactive.

Figure .2 shows the kinds of political media messages at the (We are all Khaled Said)

And by looking at the following chart on the comparison between social interactions in most admired media messages we find the following:

The comic(A.S.No,13) received the highest rates of social interaction in terms of Likes and engagement.

The percentage of likes was more than other social interaction rates, reaching 19.793, while the lowest percentage was for shares of the video(A.S.No,10) with 20 shares only.

Percentages for likes of the visual message and comic caricature were close, and the difference between the two was only 500 shares.

While the slogan(A.S.NO,12), video earned the lowest percentages in terms of Likes and participation and comments.

And a comparison between the number of followers on the page We are all Khaled Said, which amounted to 3,817,744 and highest ratios of interaction by followers, which amounted to 49 143, this difference confirms the validity of the results and the comparison

between AlKaram men of the revolution Page and we are all Khaled Said Page.

Where was the visual media message pictured on AlKaram men of the revolution Page got 1076 likes, and 244 shares, and 34 comments, and was the highest among other media messages. While the comic media message in We are all Khaled Said Page got 19,793 likes, 14,447 shares and 926 comments, and was the highest percentage in media messages on the page. This shows that media messages containing visuals and the human sense are most important catalysts for social interaction.

Where we find that the hypotheses the researcher did not prove their validity as well regarding the individual decision and the sent media message. As there is an inverse relationship and not a direct correlation between the number of views and the number of followers and between the individual decisions to participate in the social interaction of media messages.

5.2 The political awareness campaigns at CFB pages and the political motivating:

To address our second and third research questions "Did CFB pages were participated in political awareness for political elections campaigns?" and "Did the CFB pages were participated to motivating their followers?" to proved true that if there is a zero connection between social mobility and political media messages did not contribute to in mass political movement.

5.2.1 Political media awareness for the presidential election campaigns in AlKaram men of the revolution Page:

26 candidates participated in the nomination for the presidential elections in Tunisia, including three women and a thinker and a media person.

These elections were the end of the democratic transition in Tunisia, which began after the Tunisian revolution and the fall of Zine El Abidine Ben Ali's regime. These elections are also is the first presidential elections after the adoption of the new Tunisian Constitution of 2014 by the National Constituent Assembly, elected in 2011 in the first elections after the revolution that were fair and democratic, transparent and multi-party.

«For the first time in the history of Tunisia the way was opened for everyone to compete for

the presidency of the Republic, so there is a thirst to participate in this historic event» (political analyst Salah al-Din Jawrchi- Al-Quds Al-Arabi-2014)

Dr. Mohamed Moncef Marzouki, is one of the candidates for the presidency rule in Tunisia, and is a symbol of the people's revolutionary struggle against dictatorship of politicians – according to the page description of him- where he represents the Congress Party for the Republic.

He was elected temporary president of Tunisia in December 12, 2011 by the National Constituent Assembly after receiving a majority of 153 votes to three votes against, with two abstentions, and 44 white card representing 202 members from the total membership of 217. (BBC Arabia, 2011). It is noted that the AlKaram men of the revolution Page, was very biased in support of Marzouki, and did not contribute to the political awareness of the rest of the political candidates.

The Page focused on supporting Marzouki and launching supportive media campaigns to expand the scope of social interaction in the country in support of Marzouki. Most of the media messages for the campaigns were characterized by writing on the walls, and the photos (A.S.No15) of these messages were published on the Page for different regions in Tunisia in support of the supporters of the media campaign.

It is noted that the page published a set of images that emphasize the Tunisians support of Marzouki, and launched a media campaign to support Marzouki in Canada and Germany. But the campaigns and media messages launched by the Page resorted to publishing photos without commenting on the agenda of the campaign and its goals and achievements, or discussing the political message of Marzouki, for a more general awareness of the public in Tunisia or in other countries.

And it is noted that the page has relied on stimulating support for Marzouki, and making fun of the candidates' competitors. The Page did not analyze the logical reasons for their media messages as the logical analysis was expected to contribute to raising the political awareness of the receiving public, which is one of the goals of the page. We find here that the page has contradicted its intellectual orientation of being neutral and creating political awareness, which decreased its credibility among its followers.

The theme was (freedom no return to the constitutional gang) and emphasis was placed on publishing Code 24, which is Marzouki's number in the election form.

The number of media campaigns in support of Marzouki on the Page: 11 albums of visual media messages

Rates of social interaction with media campaigns on the Page:

1. Popular Campaign Committee in Tataouine: 46 like- 4 share - 7 comments

2. Tunisian community in Canada for Marzuki: 5 likes
3. grass-roots campaign in millions to support Marzouki: 59 likes- 71 shares - 4 comments
4. People's National Committee in fawar: 66 likes- 44 shares- 1 comment
5. People's National Committee in Western Mutamadyah: 26 likes - 14 shares - 1 comment
6. Educate the elderly and illiterate campaign: 7 like - 12 shares
7. Awareness campaign for the election of political parties: 60 likes - 40 shares - 4 comments
8. Today I will elect Marzouki, Germany: 1 like
9. People's Committee to support Marzouki in Carthage: 28 likes - 23 shares- 2 comments
10. I am Tunisian I am free campaign: 98 likes- 68 shares - 1 comment
11. Awareness Campaign for rigging the elections: 36 likes - 115 shares - 8 comments

Figure .3 shows the political Election campaigns at the (Thawrat Rigal Al Karm)

The highest rates of social interaction in campaigns reached 115 shares, 98 likes, 8 comments; the total number of the highest rates of social interactions was 221. In contrast the lowest ratios of social interaction in campaigns were: 1like, 1 share, 1 comment, the lowest total social interactions 3. Some media campaigns received zero social interaction. The media campaign to support Marzouki in Germany got 1 like, 0 comment, 0 share.

Figure 4. The highest and the lowest rates in the social interaction in media campaigns

If we compare the percentage of the number of followers of the Page (51 810) and the total number of the highest social interactions of the campaigns, which amounts to 221, we find that the relative difference is very big, and this confirms that there is an inverse -and not proportional- relationship between the effect of increasing political awareness among the recipient public and the role of the famous social networking sites in increasing awareness, and this proves wrong the hypothesis put forward by the researcher.

And from here we confirm that Al Karam men of the revolution Page did not contribute to the political awareness of its followers. In contrast, we find that there is a zero relationship between messages from the most popular social networking sites and social mobility, and this was confirmed by the researcher's hypothesis.

5.22 Political media awareness campaigns for the presidential elections in Egypt on We are all Khaled Said Page:

The Egyptian presidential election of 2012 is the second multi-candidate presidential election in Egypt's history, and the first presidential elections after the 25 of January revolution. The first round of elections was held on 23 and 24 May 2012, and the second round was held on 16 and 17 of June. The election schedule was decided according to announcement by the Supreme Committee for Elections; after the response from the Supreme Council of the Armed Forces to the request of speeding up the transfer of power

after Mohamed Mahmoud Street demonstrations in November 2011. (BBCArabia, 2012)
There were 13 candidates for the presidential elections and Mohamed Morsi, who represents the freedom and Justice Party, and an independent candidate Ahmed Shafiq and Hamdeen Sabahi, who represents Al Karamah party received the highest votes. The Page contributed to the socio-political marketing of the candidates, and it stepped up its efforts in the analysis of the news articles and news headlines in the election period, and it also contributed to a poll for followers about the news and political events during the nomination period.

The Page was heavily focused on the visual media messages, such as pictures of martyrs in that period, to confirm linking the message of Martyrs with choosing the president as a symbol of the revolution and to raise the political media awareness of its followers. The Page published a lot of political news from the Egyptian press archive, to link things with what happened in the fifties as a hidden message (history repeats itself).

This figure shows the most political campaigns were focused on them during the political election:

9000

8000

7000

6000

5000

4000

3000

2000

1000

0

Shaifq Campaign Sapahy Campaign Moursy

Campaign

like

shear

comment

Figure .5 shows the political Election campaigns at the (We are all Khaled Said)

It is noticeable that We are all Khaled Said Page was directed in support of Mohamed Morsi and Hamdeen and Abdel Moneim Aboul Fotouh in social marketing and political awareness, and the opposition of Ahmed Shafiq. Where equal proportions were shown in support of Morsi and Sabahi in its campaigns and media messages, and it highlighted the positive side of the candidates, in terms of democracy in their personalities and their support for the goals of the revolution. On the other hand, it clearly showed Ahmed Shafiq as a follower of the previous Hosni Mubarak regime, and considered him as his successor and as supportive of his government (A.S.No,16) The written commentary under the picture is (unfortunately the revolution succeeded, from remarks made by Ahmed Shafiq). This picture received 5501 likes, 7769 shares and 1067 comments. Most of the comments appeared in favor of the picture and in favor of discrediting the political orientation and political agenda of Ahmed Shafiq.

The Page intensified its publishing of media messages for each of Mursi and AboulFotouh and Sabahiwith (A.S.No,17) regard to their political and ideological similarities and their political agenda, while the media messages for Ahmed Shafiq questioned the credibility of the political agenda for Ahmed Shafiq. This picture received 3716 likes, 1345 shares and 688 comments.The comments were varied, as some were in favor of Hamdeen, others were rejecting him and his thoughts and his political agenda. The Page did not show any negative comments or even clear support for Mohamed Morsi in the political media awareness, but he always appeared in the presidential election period with Hamdeen and Abdel Moneim Abu al Fotouh (A.S.No18) This picture got 4539 likes, 6362 shares and 1096 comments, and the comment on the image by the page was about the most important decisions taken by the candidates three days ahead of the final elections on the law for presidential isolation.Also, the comments from the followers were varied showing political awareness of the followers, where large numbers of them were involved in the analysis of the current situation, and argued about the decisions taken by the candidates, and the timing of their decisions.

600	500	Opposes	Irreleveant	Comments	comments	Dosen't	Sapahi
		Pictures	comment	aganist	supporting	Know	Moursy
400	300			Campaign	Campaign		
200	100						
		Supports					
		Pictures					

Shafiq

Figure .6 shows the different reaction of followers comments at the (We are all Khaled Said)

The majority of followers also stressed their support for Hamdeen and Aboul Fotouh, and there wasn't any obvious support for Mohamed Morsi in the comments. In the figure above was founded that there were an equal percentage for supporting pictures and supporting campaigns at Shafiq and Sapahi campaigns, and there were nearly 30% followers support Moursy picture campaign and a small amount of interaction comments with Moursy supporting campaign. Furthermore, among the 40% against Shafiq campaign In terms of the different percentage of interactive comments Supporting Moursy campaign. Rather than Sapahi campaign collected a highest percentage for interactive comments of the page followers, he didn't had a supporting in the political election.

The followers in the pages they not reflected a reality reactions in the street, but they could be an example for a human behavior reaction for how they influence with media messages.

But the second round of presidential elections resulted in the victory of the freedom and Justice Party candidate, Mohamed Morsi, by 51.73% compared with the independent political rival, Ahmed Shafiq 48.27% .

This result confirms the following, There may be a direct correlation between the effect of increasing political awareness among the recipient audiences and the role of the famous pages on the social networking sites in increasing awareness. There may be a direct correlation between the quality of the messages from famous personalities on the social networking sites and individual decisions. And there may be a zero relationship not between the messages from famous personalities on the social networking sites and social mobility. And this confirms the hypotheses of the study.

Discussion:

Through a case study for each of Al Karam men of the revolution Page in Tunisia, and We are all Khaled Said Page in Egypt, we see the following:

The most popular pages in Facebook were not a major source or a supporting source for Arab revolutions. The media messages targeting followers didn't contribute to the mass political movement. In fact, there has always been a lack of relationship between the

political media messages on the Pages and the mass movement of followers.

Also, the pages did not contribute very significantly to the political consciousness of the followers. The source of the final decision was the individual himself and his ideological orientation and independent views. This indicates the awareness of individual who follows different sources of news and composition of his intellectual and political orientation according to his views and aspirations and individual decisions.

The most popular pages on Facebook in the two countries were a source of fragmented ideas and political agendas that support a particular political style. It violates the principle of the pages themselves. The Pages attributed to themselves the principle of intellectual freedom and political independence of expression and intellectual and political orientation, but they proved the opposite of what they claim, and this calls to questioning the credibility of their media awareness messages for their followers.

The media organization of the pages and the structured strategies of social marketing didn't contribute a lot to gaining social interaction of followers. The social interaction ratios have shown an inverse relationship between the number of followers and viewers and their social interaction with the published media messages.

The sarcasticvisual media messages gained the largest share of interaction of the followers, and this confirms that visual messages like the picture and comments have a big role in the delivery of the media message and possess direct impact for getting the expected social interaction. While written messages gets moderate ratios and are least able to deliver the direct impact of media messages.

This shows that media messages containing images and sense of humanity are the most important catalysts for social interaction, and this confirms the role of the theory of emotional intelligence, which is based on human interaction with the event, and how it employs media messages to gain supporters and broadcast motivating messages. Social interaction which was happening was the result of human sympathy and not the result of political awareness and perception of what is beyond political agendas.

And back to the typical government media in the two countries before, during and after the revolutions, we find great similarities between the alternative media (Facebook) and the government media in how to formulate the media messages and their media and intellectual style in the media marketing for its orientation and its political agenda that support its ideas and achieve the desired support. The Arab citizen has become aware of the promotional style of the political media messages.

Conclusion and Recommendations:

Many public and political analysts thought that social communication across social networking sites in particular (Facebook) is the main cause of the Arab revolutions and its support in the Arab world, but not one scientific study has been able to prove it until now. And this study might prove otherwise.

And by reference to studies and proven theories in the Arab world about Facebook's role in the political movement and political change and increasing political awareness in the Arab world, the study confirms what was confirmed by previous theories regarding the lack of interaction of the Arab street with the political media and orientation intellectual towards political change through Social Media (Facebook).

The Arab street is not yet ready to receive change through Facebook, and some social sites are contributing to expressing political views freely without social interaction for political change or to modify political agendas, according to what the study showed. That social interaction and the political movement that actually happened in the Arab Spring revolutions originated from political oppression and social injustice in the Arab street for the helpless citizen, and the maturity and the awareness of the Arab citizen of his civil and social rights, and his ability to claim them.

The study showed the extent of the Arab citizen's awareness of his political issues and his ability to distinguish between obvious political agendas and political awareness, and that the media promotion, whether by the government or alternative media did not help to change the individual decisions based on political consciousness.

Therefore, the study recommends the following:

- To respect for the mentality of the Arab citizen, and maintain credibility in the dissemination and analysis of political news in line with the culture and consciousness of the young Arab citizens, who possess a lot of scientific knowledge and technological development that makes him an effective tool in support of correct political media messages.
- Thereed to develop and mature the political media marketing strategies in the Arab world in line with the aspirations of the citizens, and his requirements and humanitarian needs in his homeland. The alternative media is an important tool for disseminating broader socio-political marketing and identifying the views of citizens regarding political decisions.

- Utilize the theory of positive emotional intelligence in support of political media messages in the Arab world. The humanitarian aspect in the Arab citizen contributes to pushing him towards positive interaction with the media and political messages.
- The need for transparency and drawing the way for Arab citizens to guide them about the political direction of the country, and take advantage of the youth awareness and intellectual openness and expertise for effective engagement in the future plans for his country.

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Appendices:

Sample (1) image:
written on the image (the
Communist terrorist
threatens his colleagues in
the Constituent Assembly
with slaughter)

Sample (2) image
bearing the slogan
(write the
constitutions you
like....the Quran and
Sunnah are our
Constitution)

Sample (3) image:
mockery of the
decision to choose the
new head of the
Tunisian government
due to old age.

Sample(4) images:
Graphical images for national unity in Egypt Sample 4a
Sample 4b

Sample (5) video capture:
The video (SamiaAbbo.. reveals a

crime of abduction and torture of suspects in the case of release) received the highest viewing , where

views reached 7,553 Views, and the video got 142 Likes, and 403 Shares, and 20 comments.

The video talks about a clip from live broadcast on the Tunisian national channel, where an MP in the Tunisian People's Assembly (SamiaAbbo) speaks about the issue of the abduction of two accused women who were tortured and hidden until the signs of torture on their bodies disappeared before being released. Most comments on this video repeats one statement; (do not forgive, no reconciliation, before holding them accountable).

Sample(6) image:

Image of a military general badly dressed.

The message on the page was (about the largest number of likes that the photo will, otherwise the page will be closed).

Most of the comments on the photo were jokes, and comments about the length of the trousers.

The image got 1076 likes, and 244 shares, and 34 comments.

Sample(7) Slogan:

The slogan was (the Revolution is owned by the

Tunisian people)
And the comments and
assertions about the
Casbah revolution in the
December 17, 2013, were a
confirmation of the
continuation of the
Tunisian revolution against
political corruption.
This picture got 688 likes,
148 shares and 13
comments

Sample(8) comic:

The caricature carries and
portrays the Casbah
revolution slogan, and the
message directed by page,
called for (the need to
print the caricature and
publish it to the largest
possible sector in
confirmation of the
solidarity with the Casbah
revolution).

This caricature got 122
Likes, 89 shares and 2
comments only.

Sample(9) Quote:

It got 105 likes, 138 shares
and 4 comments

A statement of the late
jihadist Omar al-Mukhtar: "Be
a proud and never bend no
matter how necessary it
maybe ... as you might not get
the opportunity to raise your

head again."

Sample(10)video capture:

2,107 likes, 20 shares and
848 comments

A section of the live
broadcast of Al Jazeera
news channel about
Egyptians gathered in
Tahrir Square on February
7, 2011

And the synchronization of
Muslim prayer and
Christian hymns. Most of
the comments asserted
that this picture is
evidence of the national
unity of the Egyptian
people.

sample(11) Image:

13,090 likes, 4,549 shares and
1,277 comments
This image was taken in July 1,
2013 and this image shows a large
crowd of the Egyptian people in a
street in the capital Cairo.

This crowd has come out to confirm
and support the government
decision to remove President
Mohamed Morsi and handover
power to the Egyptian army for an
interim period. The page merely put
the picture as a visual media
message to express event without
comment from the page, and the

followers' comments revealed their support of this image.

sample(12) Slogan:

4,153 likes, 823 shares and 774

comments

(No going back) is the slogan used to confirm the demands of the revolution of January 25, 2011 and which had raised the slogan (living, freedom, social justice, human dignity.). This media message appeared in June 24, 2013. Comments showed that the followers are split between supporters of the slogan, who support the January 25 Revolution, and those who suspect the credibility of achieving the dream as described by some, and those who oppose the media message because the reality doesn't reflect the January 25 revolution slogan.

Sample(13) Comic:

19,793 likes, 14,447 shares and 926 comments

The media message appeared in this caricature as the image of a very wealthy obese man who carries binoculars to look for the poor and he doesn't see them. And under his big stomach we see the hungry poor trying to draw his attention. The comment on the caricature was (where are the poor? I do not see them!!).

And most of the comments were just laughter, and answers to a question posed in the caricature.

But the media message in this caricature, which was published in the July 30, 2012, during electricity blackouts and gasoline shortage in Egypt, demonstrates that the biggest sector affected by this crisis are the poor, and that the upper class is hardly affected by the crisis in the country.

Sample(14) Quote:

10,000 likes and 487

comments

This argument for Dr. Mustafa

Mahmoud got the highest

ratios of admiration from the

followers. The political media

message it carried described

faith and the hope for change.

And it said (who reads

history...despair does not

enter his heart ever, and will

see that God alternates the

days between people, people

exchange their chairs, and that

no sadness lasts ... and no joy

lasts).

Sample(15) Images from Album: It is

noted that the AlKaram men of the

revolution Page, was very biased in

support of Marzouki, and did not contribute to

the political awareness of the rest of the

political candidates. The Page focused on

supporting Marzouki and launching supportive

media campaigns to expand the scope of social

interaction in the country in support of

Marzouki. Most of the media messages for the

campaigns were characterized by writing on the

walls, and the photos of these messages were

published on the Page for different regions in

Tunisia in support of the supporters of the

media campaign.

Sample(16) Shafiq Campaign Image:

Headline shows picture of Hosni

Mubarak saying words of Ahmed

Shafiq

The written commentary under the

picture is (unfortunately the

revolution succeeded, from remarks

made by Ahmed Shafiq). This

picture received 5501 likes, 7769 shares and 1067 comments.

Most of the comments appeared in favor of the picture and in favor of discrediting the political orientation and political agenda of Ahmed Shafiq.

Sample(17) Sapahi Camping Image:

Hamdeen between his supporters in Tahrir Square.

This picture received 3716 likes, 1345 shares and 688 comments

The comments were varied, as some were in favor of Hamdeen, others were rejecting him and his thoughts and his political agenda.

Sample(18) MursiCampaign Image:

picture of Hamdeen - Mursi and AboulFotouh

This picture got 4539 likes, 6362 shares and 1096 comments

And the comment on the image by the page was about the most important decisions taken by the candidates three days ahead of the final elections on the law for presidential isolation.

And the comments from the followers were varied showing political awareness of the followers, where large numbers of them were involved in the analysis of the current situation, and argued about the decisions taken by the candidates, and the timing of their decisions.